

sEEnergies

QUANTIFICATION OF SYNERGIES BETWEEN ENERGY EFFICIENCY FIRST
PRINCIPLE AND RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEMS

D1.3

Report on economic and social impact assessment of Energy Efficiency measures in the building sector

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
BT	Building type
EE	Energy efficiency
ERA	Energy Reference Area
GDP	Gross domestic product
GVA	Gross value added
MFH	Multi-family house
NPV	Net present value
RES	Renewable energy sources
SFH	Single-family house
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

Analyses of energy efficiency measures usually focus on direct savings of useful or final energy in different economic sectors or energy-related appliances.¹ In this report, we focus on energy savings and other related benefits of efficiency improvements in the built environment. In the deliverables 1.1 and 1.2 (Reiter et al., 2020, 2021) the costs and efficiency gains of different refurbishment measures for buildings have been analysed, but other benefits have been neglected so far. Thereby non-energy related impacts such as comfort and productivity improvements due to better insulated windows and better ventilation systems or noise reductions in sleeping or office rooms due to better insulated building envelopes are often excluded or not sufficiently taken into account (Skumatz et al., 2000). For various sectors this exclusion of additional benefits can lead to a significant underestimation and under-appreciation of energy efficiency investments (IEA, 2014). In many cases, the appropriate valuation of such additional benefits could reinforce drivers and counterbalance barriers to more energy efficiency investments (Rasmussen, 2017). In residential and commercial buildings, additional benefits could add up to 60-100% to previous estimates of the benefits of energy efficiency measures in monetary terms (Skumatz et al., 2000). Therefore, considering non-energy benefits can strongly increase the profitability of energy efficiency measures and hence should be an essential part of every energy efficiency assessment.

In addition to these non-energy benefits, rebound effects can influence the profitability of energy efficiency investments in the opposite direction, i.e., increasing energy demand or lowering the expected efficiency gains (Hertwich, 2005). Under circumstances, a trade-off between social and economic benefits and energy savings can occur (IEA, 2012). Therefore, rebound effects are just as important to consider as non-energy benefits. This can be a challenging task given that such features are, same as non-energy benefits, often difficult to measure and to quantify due to their non-market nature (Mills & Rosenfeld, 1996) or they occur outside the boundary condition of the specific efficiency analysis. However, it is recommended to spend further resources on obtaining such information as it can serve as an essential basis for private and policy decisions as well as marketing strategies (Skumatz et al., 2000).

As introduced in deliverable 1.2 of this work package (Reiter et al., 2021), energy efficiency improvements resulting from refurbishment measures in the residential building sector and related cost savings were analysed and presented. To gain a more comprehensive comparison of the considered energy efficiency measures, their social and economic benefits as well as their rebound effects should be considered as well. In the following report, we will propose a framework to assess non-energy related benefits such as comfort, less energy poverty, health, behavioural aspects, labour productivity etc., and substantiate it for selected cases. The goal is to present some further quantifications of non-energy benefits and therefore to provide a clearer picture of economic and social costs and benefits of the proposed energy efficiency measures.

It must be mentioned that only a limited number of additional benefits can be quantified in this work package as only the efficiency gains of useful energy demand have been calculated. Therefore, final energy demand related savings such as savings on fuel expenditures cannot be considered and we

¹ This differentiation between useful and final energy is necessary to understand the impact of conversion efficiencies of energy appliances and losses within the distribution system on the overall energy consumption.

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refer to the additional benefits analysis of work package six (WP6) which will highlight additional benefits from various sources.

2 Methods and Approach

Basis for the analysis in WP1 is the methodology described in (Fleiter et al., 2017) on modelling the energy demand from the building stock in Europe using the bottom-up modelling approach of the FORECAST model family. In the sEnergies project, we included additional improvements to this methodology which are described in more detail in the deliverables 1.1 and 1.2 (Reiter et al., 2020, 2021). The relation to the other work packages of this project is also shown in deliverable 1.2 as it is the basis to understand the boundary conditions for the quantification of non-energy benefits in the built environment. For this deliverable (1.3) the same scope is assumed as for deliverable 1.2, meaning that the analysis covers all 28 countries of the European Union including the UK as well as 10 residential buildings typologies, separated in 2 building types and 5 building construction periods as well as services sector buildings. The different building typologies can undergo a set of 15 different refurbishment measures, which are also described in more detail in deliverable 1.2. The efficiency gains based on the defined measures are also basis for the quantification of non-energy benefits.

The underlying methodology for this deliverable (1.3) is based on the quantification of measures implemented in deliverable 1.2 and the associated investment costs. By using the underlying building stock as well as the set of refurbishment measures, we will try to quantify selected non-energy benefits. To give an overview of potential non-energy benefits in the built environment, we conducted a comprehensive literature review, which will be introduced in the following paragraphs. Based on the list of non-energy benefits, we select those measures which we can quantify either by the relation to the building stock or alternatively based on the respective refurbishment measures.

2.1 Non-energy impacts

The non-energy benefits related to the building stock can be categorized into three main categories. First and most obvious non-energy impacts can be grouped under economic impacts as they can be directly linked to economic effects either by the reduction of expenditures or increased revenues from the investors. Second and more difficult to quantify are social and behavioural or personal benefits which are related to well-being and the comfort of the environment we are living and working in. We group these benefits under social impacts although this expression might be implying too narrow a view. The third group of impacts are grouped under the so-called rebound effects which might lead to either higher expenditures or consumption of the specific demand or even counteracting specific energy efficiency measures. In the following, we will discuss the named benefits further.

2.1.1 Economic Impacts

The direct economic impacts of energy efficiency measures are the cost savings associated with energy savings which are not in the focus of this work. However, there are other, less obvious economic impacts which should be considered in cost-benefit analyses as well. Some of the main direct economic impacts are an increased disposable income and job creation as described in (IEA, 2012; Schweitzer & Tonn, 2003; Skumatz et al., 2000), amongst others.

Regarding the disposable income, especially in low-income households, more energy efficiency leads to better energy affordability and energy access which in turn can lead to poverty alleviation (IEA, 2012; Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007). In this respect, the tenant - landlord dilemma as well as unfavourable pricing regimes for energy are of high relevance (see also (Klinke et al., 2017)) as such barriers are delimiting the potential cost reduction of low-income households as they are typically renting their premises and cannot profit from respective savings. As landlords need to invest in energy efficiency, only some parts of the additional investment costs can be covered by increased rents and therefore, the interest in such investments is reduced.

To quantify such impacts on disposable income, we suggest combining information on the social context or income classification of building users together with the number of refurbished dwellings or buildings of such users and the related floor area as well as with the refurbishment depth and the related energy costs savings of such refurbishment measures. Therefore, the equation proposed by (Reuter et al., 2020a) can be adjusted for the differences in energy efficiency gains in low income housing by adjusting for the higher than average efficiency gains:

$$\sum_1^n \Delta Inc_{BT} = - \sum_1^n ec * ES_{HH,BT,ERA}$$

Where ΔInc_{BT} is the difference in the disposable income in dependence of the building type (BT) and the available energy reference area (ERA). This difference in disposable income can be aggregated on country level for the specific building typologies and dwelling size classes. Depending on the energy savings per building type ($ES_{HH,BT,ERA}$) and the energy cost (ec), households can profit differently from such efficiency improvements and therefore, the difference in the disposable income varies.

However, the combination of such information on low-income households, as well as their related living standards, building typologies and additional living information (e.g., energy reference area, building age, building code, building location, etc.) on country level is not yet available in European wide building stock-related models. Some countries provide such information (e.g., Denmark) which can be taken up for quantifications. In addition to the findings of (Reuter et al., 2020a) the proposed approach would allow to quantify the differences also in absolute terms for the whole building stock in a country. However, first country specific indices need to be developed to evaluate the fuel poverty related to building standards (Fabbri, 2015).

Other important positive effects of energy efficiency improvements arise due to additional cost benefits from down-sizing of equipment. This means for example that less HVAC and heating power is needed as a result of reduced transmission of radiation in more efficient windows (Skumatz et al., 2000). The increase in disposable income leads to additional societal benefits related to multiplier effects, meaning that money no longer spent on energy can be spent on alternative goods and services. However, it must be considered, that investments need to be paid back and therefore reduce the savings from energy efficiency measures. Depending on payback times, the additional income increases with time. From this, an additional macroeconomic impact on the whole society (Schweitzer & Tonn, 2003) can result.

These effects on disposable income highly depend on the energy prices. If overall efficiency measures lead to reduced energy demand, e.g., on country level, then energy prices might decline and further increase the availability of disposable income. However, other factors such as production decrease or increasing demand for energy services due to overall economic growth might impact the energy prices

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in opposite direction, influencing the effects on disposable income (IEA, 2014). Such additional impacts hold true for other scenarios as well and are therefore neglected in this analysis.

Besides the disposable income, the energy efficiency standard of buildings can also affect the asset value of the respective building (Schweitzer & Tonn, 2003; Skumatz et al., 2000). The reduced energy demand is reducing the impact of volatile energy prices on the overall annual budget of building owners and tenants and therefore reduces the risk for budget overspending (see also Table 2). In more recent work (Fuerst et al., 2015), or (Khazal & Sønstebø, 2020), the increased property value as well as increased rental prices can be expected to be in the range of 3 to 5 % higher for higher performing buildings compared to low efficiency buildings, respectively.

Besides the described impact on disposable income and asset values, other non-energy benefits can be aggregated under economic aspects. On a national level, energy efficiency measures can on the one hand influence the gross domestic product (GDP) positively or negatively, depending on whether energy commodities are produced domestically, or being imported. On the other hand, they can also increase energy security through reduced energy imports and relieved pressure on scarce resources as well as a higher system reliability due to the smaller energy demand (IEA, 2012; Mills & Rosenfeld, 1996). In combination with the approach to tax energy demand (energy taxes and levies), countries need to prepare for changes in their revenue stream. However, the benefits of reduced import dependency are more of a strategic asset and policy relevant and therefore not to quantify under the viewpoints of building stock modelling.

All these factors, especially the increased disposable income as well as the higher asset values, lead to a potential increase in public budgets due to higher tax incomes, and therefore more capital is available which can be reinvested into other national sectors (IEA, 2014).

However, one must keep in mind that such non-energy related gains are often reduced or not available to the low-income households and others as the split-incentive barrier is not appropriately addressed. According to (Castellazzi et al., 2017), split incentives can be defined as failure of distributing costs and benefits of e.g., energy efficiency investments amongst the actors in an effective manner. The authors differentiated between four different types of split incentives which are “efficiency split incentives”, “usage-related split incentives”, “temporal split incentives” as well as “multi-tenant, multi-owner split incentives” (Castellazzi et al., 2017). Additionally, one can add the “capital reverse split incentive” which is that building owners have the need to maintain their capital by maintaining and upgrading their property while tenants do not have this need. However, under current circumstances, building owners face favourable conditions with better access to capital, low interest rates and additional subsidies and interest reductions in case of energetic refurbishments of the building stock ().

The split incentive principally only concerns rented premises as in owned and self-used buildings, investors profit from reduced energy bills directly. Therefore, the focus group of buildings are multi-family houses (no condominiums) and rented office space. In a study from 2017 (Iten, Wunderlich, et al., 2017), the authors investigate the cost sharing between owners and tenants in multi-family houses in Switzerland in the case of heating system exchange. Depending on the national regulations, higher costs of renewable heating systems might be transferred if old fossil-based heating systems are replaced by new renewable systems. This cost transfer does not apply in case of replacing fossil systems by new fossil heating systems and neither in case of new buildings. As in WP1 of this project, we are looking into the costs of refurbishment measures of the building envelope, where similar rules apply: Only the part of the investment cost which is seen as value added for the tenant can be

transferred within the rent or variable cost increase. Other cost parts which are related to maintaining the status quo of the building cannot be transferred. As there is no clear definition and differentiation between effects which are clearly value adding and the effects which maintain the status of the building, the barrier remains, as the investor has a clear information advantage and is likely to transfer higher cost shares towards the tenants.

Additionally, the split incentive differs depending on the building age class as well as the building status of the existing building and the country specific investment cost level. As shown in deliverable 1.1 (Reiter et al., 2020), the net present value (NPV) of refurbishment measures is positive or only slightly negative for most buildings built before the years 1991. In this case it can be shown that depending on the cost transfer from investor to tenant, both groups face equal or only slightly higher costs in case of refurbishment compared to a non-energy efficient overhaul of the building. This is valid if investment costs for the envelope can be transferred by up to 70% to the tenant and up to 50% in case of new windows (see also (Iten, Wunderlich, et al., 2017)).

However, in case of buildings with existing building codes (i.e., built after 1991) which are refurbished to higher than current minimum standards (e.g., to a level of passive house standard), the additional costs for tenants and owners are higher in any case of envelope refurbishment. Therefore, the interest in refurbishing such buildings is reduced also under the aspects of split incentives as not all additional costs can be transferred to the tenant.

2.1.2 Social Impacts

There are various social benefits that can be a by-product of energy efficiency measures. The most frequently mentioned ones concern health, safety and comfort of inhabitants (IEA, 2014; Schweitzer & Tonn, 2003; Skumatz et al., 2000). Reducing indoor and outdoor air pollution directly improves public health, meaning less disability-adjusted life years lost as well as fewer lost work days (Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007). But not only reduced pollution levels affect residents' health, but also reduced moisture problems due to better windows (Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007). Additionally, many energy efficiency measures in residential buildings increase thermal comfort, for example through better-insulated windows (Mills & Rosenfeld, 1996; Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007). But insulation activities not only improve the thermal environment, but can also have a reducing effect on noise pollution (Mills & Rosenfeld, 1996; Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007). Better safety was mainly mentioned in combination with more fire-proof windows and insulation materials which proved to be safer in case of a fire event (Mills & Rosenfeld, 1996).

All these aspects contribute to higher overall comfort, which can lead to higher well-being and productivity of the residents (Mills & Rosenfeld, 1996; Skumatz et al., 2000). But not only the society profits from energy efficiency measures, but also the environment through the reduction of GHG emissions (IEA, 2012; Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007). However, most studies categorize this as a social benefit, given that it has a strong effect on the health and well-being of the residents as well as very far-reaching positive consequences on the whole society.

However, there are other developments which are rather negative in terms of social effects and energy efficiency investments. In the past, several publications investigate the impact of refurbishment measures on gentrification in urban areas (see e.g., (Bouzarovski et al., 2018; Checker, 2011; Rice et al., 2020)). Based on local experience from often state induced refurbishment programs, gentrification is taking place in urban areas. This gentrification is driven by several factors which can be differentiated

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into pure energetic refurbishment measures and e.g., increased surface areas, increased dwelling standards and others after demolition and new construction of existing buildings. The quantification of such effects is based on drivers such as demolition rate, local context of buildings, average dwelling size before and after refurbishment and others. Based on our model framework, the lack of specific data on local context and building structure hinders the quantification of such impacts but can be considered in case specific building stock models include such information in the future.

2.1.3 Overview of all non-energy benefits

In Table 1 all non-energy benefits that are mentioned in section 2.1.1 and 2.1.2 are listed. Additionally, for each one a short description or an illustrative showcase is given to clarify how these benefits are obtained. Furthermore, the reference of the given information is mentioned in the third column.

Table 1 Overview of the most important non-energy benefits of energy efficiency measures in residential buildings with explanatory showcases

Non-energy Benefit	Showcase	Reference
Increased disposable income	The relative change of disposable income due to energy efficiency measures in residential buildings is by far the highest in low-income households, where they can increase by up to 50%, compared to high-income households where it might even decrease.	(Figus et al., 2017)
Job creation	RE and EE are more labour intensive in terms of electricity generated or saved than traditional fossil-fuel generation. Therefore, building refurbishment can lead to a net job creation.	(Blyth et al., 2014; Iten, Jakob, et al., 2017)
Higher Property and rental prices	In a case study in Italy, they found that when a building gets the best energy performance label, its value can increase by approximately 27%.	(Morano et al., 2020)
Increased energy security	Energy prices are dependent on fossil fuel prices. Given that these are very variable, especially of crude oil, reducing their usage stabilizes energy prices and the dependence on other countries' economies.	(Gamtessa & Olani, 2018)
GDP	Energy efficiency can increase the GDP and economic activity up to a point that household incomes profit more from this GDP growth than from the efficiency improvement itself.	(Figus et al., 2017)

Increase in public budgets	Public budgets can be significantly increased through higher tax income or through energy savings due to energy efficiency measures in public buildings.	(Annunziata et al., 2014; Kuckshinrichs et al., 2010)
Thermal comfort and its impacts on health and safety	The health of residents mainly benefits from energy efficiency due to a reduction of cold-related illnesses and associated stress. Especially low-income households and children are positively affected.	(Maidment et al., 2014)
Reduced indoor and outdoor air pollution	Inadequate ventilation and fossil heating systems are primary causes of indoor air pollution. The positive impact of upgrading ventilation systems heavily depends on the outdoor air quality, which can be enhanced by reducing the burning of volatile content solid fuels.	(Spiru & Simona, 2017)
Reduced noise pollution	The ability of insulation materials to absorb outdoor noise correlates with their capacity to reduce thermal transmission.	(Pisello et al., 2016)
Improved productivity and reduced health impact	Reducing overheating in buildings can enhance employees' performance by up to 3.5%. However, avoiding too cold temperatures increases productivity through reduced illness and stress. Additionally, improved ventilation rates are favourable for reducing illness, improving concentration levels and others.	(Kockat et al., 2018; Maidment et al., 2014)

2.1.4 Rebound Effects

When a study aims at including all direct and indirect costs and benefits of energy efficiency measures, an essential part of the analysis should consider rebound effects. However, in many former studies, just like co-benefits, rebound effects are not considered enough (Hertwich, 2005). There are different drivers which can lead to rebound effects (IEA, 2014):

- Take-back effect: energy users increase their consumption to raise their comfort.
- Spending effect: households spend financial savings of reduced energy consumption for other energy-consuming activities.
- Investment effect: investment in energy efficiency leads to an overall increase in economic activity and energy consumption.

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Often, rebound effects are difficult to isolate from other processes (Greening et al., 2000). However, it is important not to try to oversimplify the dynamics regarding rebound effects too much (IEA, 2012). Also, rebound effects regarding energy consumption should not always be classified as a negative side-effect of energy efficiency measures, because energy savings are only one outcome. So, for example energy efficiency measures can reduce indoor air pollution even though, due to rebound effects, final energy consumption increases. In such a case, the measures are still beneficial, not regarding energy savings but regarding air pollution. So depending on the strategies and priorities of a government, it makes sense to invest in energy efficiency measures even though the energy consumption is in the end not reduced due to rebound effects (IEA, 2012).

2.2 Quantification

Many approaches exist to quantify non-energy benefits from refurbishment measures in buildings. One typology of quantifications is looking into the “willingness to pay” by consumers and investors to gain or profit from specific efficiency measures.

2.2.1 Economic and social impacts

In existing literature multiple ways of quantifying non-energy benefits can be found. However, most of them are based on surveys or empirical research, which are not part of this work. There are also studies which synthesized existing research to aggregate available data regarding the range of these benefits. One of those is Schweitzer & Tonn (2003), which considered multiple former studies to identify a range of monetary values for each non-energy benefit per household. From those, they derived reasonable point estimates which represent the average value of such benefit for a standardized retrofitted household. However, these data could not be used for this analysis, given that Schweitzer & Tonn (2003) focused on the US in the years 1994 – 2003 and these numbers could look quite different nowadays in the EU.

A similar approach was taken by Kockat et al. (2018), who quantified non-energy benefits in schools, offices and hospitals. The results were quite detailed benchmark values regarding how e.g., the performance of students changes when the room temperature decreases by 1°C. This was done for various non-energy indicators like workers’ and students’ performance, patients’ length of stay and employee turnover depending on increases in daylight and electric light as well as ventilation, temperature, and noise changes. This makes it possible to quantify non-energy benefits when these factors are known. Nonetheless, for this study the findings of Kockat et al. (2018) have not been used because either the data on country level is not available from our model calculations (e.g., changes in ventilation rates due to refurbishment measures) or differs from the considered parameters in (Kockat et al., 2018) (e.g., school type differentiation for primary, middle or high school, building age classes and installation of ventilation and air conditioning systems, amongst others). However, the synthesis of Kockat et al. (2018) provided useful ranges of non-energy benefits which should be analysed further in combination of specific building stock modelling to better quantify non-energy benefits on country level.

Compared to Kockat et al. (2018), Reuter et al. (2020) did not provide specific quantifications of non-energy benefits but determines equations as proxy for the different non-energy benefits. In combination with the respective data on country level, these equations can be used to quantify non-energy benefits (see Table 2).

We summarize in an overview the most relevant indicators related to the building sector based on (Reuter et al., 2020a) which are quantifiable within the scope of this project. However, due to the overall project approach with the partial integrated system model available, not all quantifications are to be implemented within this work package. Additionally, where applicable, we adapt the equations to the available building related parameters. The overview defines the indicator which can be quantified based on the calculation approach and indicates within which type of model is needed to derive the respective parameters.

Table 2 Calculation approach for non-energy benefit indicators in the building sector, including where they were applied in this project (based on (Reuter et al., 2020a)). Equations applicable on country level.

Indicator	Calculation Approach	Applicable in
Final energy savings	$EES_{j,BT} = \sum_j EES_{useful,H,BT} * \eta_{H,BT}$ <p>EES_{useful} = Energy efficiency savings of useful energy demand per building heat supply system (HS) and building type (BT) η_H = conversion efficiency of heating system typology</p>	System model, $EES_{useful,BT}$ based on WP1
Saving of fossil fuels	$EES_{fossil,j,BT} = \sum_{BT} EES_{useful,H,BT} * \eta_{H,BT,j} * \frac{FEC_{j,i}}{FEC_{total}}$ <p>EES = Energy efficiency savings (j = fossil energy carrier, BT = building type) FEC = final energy consumption per building sector (i) and fossil energy carrier (j)</p>	System model, $EES_{useful,BT}$ based on WP1
Impact of EE on RES target achievement in the building sector	$\Delta RES_{target} = actual\ RES\ share - \frac{FEC_{RES\ final,BT}}{FEC_{total,wo,BT}}$ <p>$FEC_{total,wo,BT}$ = Final energy consumption from buildings without savings (total, wo, BT) calculated based on “frozen efficiency scenario”</p>	System model, $UE_{total,wo,BT}$ based on WP1
Avoided CO ₂ emissions from energy savings per building type	$EM_{BT} = EES_{fossil,j,BT} * emf_j$ <p>EM_{BT} = CO₂-emissions per building type (BT) emf_j = average emission factor for energy carrier j</p>	System model
(Local) air pollution per m ² ERA and year per building type	$E_n = \frac{\sum_j EES_j * emf_{j,n}}{ERA_{BT}}$ <p>E_k = Emissions of pollutant n per building type ERA_{BT} = Energy reference area per building type</p>	System model, ERA_{BT} based on WP1
Turnover of energy efficiency goods in the building sector for building envelope measures	$TO_{BT} = EES_{BT} * SSH * f_{in} * IN_{env,BT}$ <p>EES = Energy savings per building type SSH = share of space heating in national energy consumption f = share of savings due to insulation & efficient heating systems IN = investments in refurbishment measures of the building envelope per building type and per unit of energy saved</p>	WP1

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Impact of sector specific GVA on GDP	$\frac{GVA(TO)_{Sec} + taxes_{Sec} - subsidies_{Sec}}{GDP_{tot}}$ <p>GVA(TO)_{Sec} = Sector specific gross value added related to building refurbishment measures and turnover</p>	System model, potential indication of GVA based on WP1
Impact on Public Budgets due to reduced demand in public buildings	<p>Calculate monetary savings that are available due to energy savings in public buildings:</p> $FES_{EE} = ERA_{Pb} * f_{in} * SUEd_{PB} * \eta_{HS,BT,j}$ <p>FES = Final energy savings in public buildings ERA = Energy reference area for public buildings (Pb) per country f = share of savings due to insulation & efficient heating systems SUEd = Specific useful energy demand per building typology of public buildings $\eta_{HS,BT,j}$ = Efficiency of the heating system per building typology and energy carrier</p>	System model, SH _{Pb} based on WP1
Asset Value of buildings aggregated on country level	$\Delta AV = \frac{\sum_j^n FES_j * p_j}{cr}$ <p>FES_j = Final energy savings per year and energy carrier P_j = price for each energy carrier j cr = capitalisation rate n = number of buildings/dwellings</p>	System model, number of buildings/dwellings based on WP1
Health benefits (avoided premature deaths)	$AD_{n,BT} = \Delta EM_{n,BT,HS} * cf * m_i$ <p>AD_n = avoided premature deaths related to pollutant n EM_{n,BT,HS} = reduced emissions of the pollutant in relation to ERA and HS per building type (BT) cf = concentration factor m_n = mortality rate of the pollutant</p>	System model, $\Delta EM_{n,BT,HS}$ based on input on ERA from WP1

However, other quantifications regarding building related energy demand (see Table 3 based on (Reuter et al., 2020b)), cannot be carried out within the scope of this project as respective information is not available within the model system. Parameters such as income or income categories in relation to building type and building standard, potential different use cases for dwellings are not part of the scope of work. Also, all impacts related to competitiveness and import dependency had to be excluded given that energy imports and exports were not analysed.

Table 3 Non-quantifiable parameters within the setup of the scope of work. Parameter definition based on (Reuter et al., 2020a) adjusted for building sector demand.

Indicator	Parameter Definition	Not Applicable (reason)
Import dependency per building sector	Dependency of the building sector on foreign fuel suppliers. Share of energy demand imported compared to fuel demand in the building sector.	Energy imports and exports per sector (i) are not part of system model

Supplier diversity per building sub-sector	Indicator to assess energy security, assumes that saved primary energy reduce imports from main suppliers. Breakdown on building sub-sector.	The origin of the energy and energy suppliers are not considered
Integration of renewables in the building sector.	Shows the demand response potential per country, meaning shifting energy services to counteract increased feed-in or bottlenecks in production due to RES integration. Breakdown on building sector of sub-sector.	No integration of demand response in the scope of work.
Employment effects	Net employment gains are likely to occur when shifting from spending on energy consumption to investing in EE measures. Positive effects are expected in the construction, material, and services sub-sectors.	The result data does not provide sufficient insights on the material needs in correlation to the efficiency improvement of the building envelope. Insights into employment related effects based on efficiency investments can be found in (Iten, Jakob, et al., 2017).
Potential impacts on energy prices	With falling demand due to energy savings, energy prices should decline. The sector specific impact on energy price changes can be estimated.	No macro-economic modelling is considered in this project
Competitiveness Impact	New development of materials, services, and goods in the field of energy efficiency.	No insights into material flows, innovation and new services or products in the scope of work.
Disposable household income in residential buildings and disposable revenues in services sector	Due to energy savings, disposable household income and services sector revenues increase. Rebound effects and use pathways for disposable income per building sub-sector.	Neither different income categories for each building type and building sub-sectors, nor revenue classifications or cost shares of energy in services sector are part of the system model. More detailed building stock model needed.
Alleviation of energy poverty	The share of energy costs compared to household income is higher for low-income households as compared to high-income households. Reducing energy costs can help reducing energy poverty.	Income categories and the relation to building standards and building age classes are not part of the model environment

2.2.2 Rebound effects

The quantification of rebound effects is a challenging task for which no universal methods exist yet. Clinch & Healy (2003) propose three-step approach of dealing with rebound effects:

- Assume a situation in which all dwellings are heated to conditions that are recommended for optimal thermal comfort.
- Assume that the occupant's spending on heating does not change compared to present levels, so they will increase their comfort by investing the monetary savings of energy efficiency measures.
- Combine the two previous models by taking a model which reflects the likelihood that rising living standards will result in increasing internal temperatures and hot water consumption, even if no energy-saving measures are implemented.

The first two steps only partially represent reality, because former studies have already shown that there are big differences in behaviour patterns of high-income and low-income households. Several European studies have found that higher income households tend to reduce their household energy expenditure after improving their dwellings' thermal efficiency, while in lower income households, energy consumption appears to remain at roughly the same level in order to increase their comfort (Chitnis et al., 2014; Clinch & Healy, 2003b; Madlener & Hauertmann, 2012).

Additionally, the usage-related split incentives (Castellazzi et al., 2017) play a crucial role for the level of rebound effects. Depending on the transparency of the heating costs for the tenant (either warm or cold rent) the rebound effect is likely to be higher in cases where the tenant is not aware of the potential heat savings after refurbishment as he has hardly any insights into the cost details. Additionally, if monthly down-payments are agreed between landlord and tenant, the balancing invoice on heating costs after one year of heat demand is disconnected from actual behaviour and therefore, the direct link between refurbishment measure and heating demand reduction is difficult to track down.

3 Results

The turnover of energy efficiency goods can be linked to the specific investment cost per building type that is generated by energy efficiency measures in residential buildings (see section 2.2.1). As can be seen in the corresponding equation in Table 2, measures with high investment costs result in a high turnover. Therefore, comprehensive building refurbishment measures including all envelope components (e.g., walls, windows and roof or basement) result in the largest turnovers. Additionally, the building age and building standard influences the necessary additional insulation material needed to achieve specific energy savings, and therefore, the turnover varies.

Based on the cost curves derived in this project (Reiter et al., 2020), the turnover for the additional efficiency gains compared to the baseline scenario (Reiter et al., 2021) can be calculated depending on the set of additional refurbishment measures implemented. An overview of the specific investment costs of the available building refurbishment packages is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** It covers typical single and multi-family houses, resp. (SFH and MFH) built between 1961 and 1990 in the example of France; other data can be found in the respective open data set. As can be seen, the building geometry influences the specific investment cost up to a factor of two between SFH and MFH,

as well as the efficiency gains influence the cost per kWh saved. Depending on the overall building stock, the building age, the building typology, and the energy saved, the overall turnover will vary between countries.

Figure 1 Specific investment cost per m² energy reference area (ERA) for the envelope per building, showing the results for an average SFH and MFH in France, built between 1961 - 1990.

As introduced above, the investment cost for refurbishment measures is usually carried by either the building owner or the tenants, neglecting the alternative of energy performance contracting (see (Klinke et al., 2017)). In case of refurbishment measures of the building envelope, a relevant share of the investment needs to be carried by the building owner as it is often difficult to distinguish, which share of the investment is needed to maintain the capital stock of the owner and which share has a direct benefit for the tenant. In the case where additional energy savings need to be achieved beyond the baseline, i.e., beyond the regulatory minimum, the landlord-tenant split incentive becomes even more apparent. As the cheapest refurbishment measures are already implemented, the incremental cost for further measures increases whereas the efficiency gains decrease. Therefore, it is in the interest of the landlord to pass-on the maximum possible of the additional cost on the tenant, as the tenant mostly profits from the additional savings as the energy bill decreases². However, in many countries, passing on the full cost on the tenants is difficult to achieve, as open formulations are used to define the cases when costs can be transferred. Therefore, clear definitions are needed to which extent the additional costs can be transferred, e.g., definitions for “sustainable energy demand reductions”, the “use value of the flat sustainably increases”, etc. (see § 556 and 559 German BGB, respectively).

² Due to the project setup, the reduction in energy cost is not considered in this work package and therefore not reflected in the calculations and figures.

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Depending on the set of refurbishment measures which are implemented for the whole building stock per country, the overall additional investments per additional savings target is calculated (see Table 4). These additional investments can be considered as additional turnover in different economic sub-sectors and categories. In Europe, in average 58% to 61% of this additional turnover can be classified as direct labour cost for installation and on-site work for the refurbishment, whereas the remaining 42% to 39%, resp. are material costs for e.g., the production of insulation material and transport on site.

Table 4 Additional investments to achieve additional energy savings compared to the baseline for the years 2030 and 2050 in Mrd. €.

Member State	Additional savings from 2030 Baseline					Additional savings from 2050 Baseline				
	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%
AT	2	6	13	15	17	1	2	6	11	13
BE	2	4	8	13	16	1	2	3	6	8
BG	1	1	2	2	3	1	2	3	4	5
CR	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
CY	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
CZ	1	2	3	4	5	1	3	4	5	6
DK	2	6	13	15	17	1	3	5	11	12
EE	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
FI	3	8	12	17	19	1	4	7	14	15
FR	10	22	35	52	85	5	11	17	29	39
DE	17	46	85	126	159	7	19	32	56	85
EL	0	1	2	4	4	0	1	1	2	4
HU	1	3	3	4	5	1	2	4	5	4
IE	1	4	7	10	11	1	1	2	4	7
IT	11	35	58	71	82	9	32	49	68	82
LV	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
LT	0	1	2	2	3	1	2	2	3	2
LU	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
MT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NL	3	10	12	20	30	2	4	6	12	16
PL	3	8	10	13	16	3	6	12	15	14
PT	1	1	3	4	5	1	1	2	3	5

RO	1	2	3	3	4	2	3	5	6	5
SK	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
SI	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
ES	8	21	36	43	54	5	15	38	45	51
SE	6	17	27	41	49	3	8	17	31	41
UK	17	45	74	106	123	7	16	37	70	91
Total	92	245	413	573	721	55	140	260	409	512

To calculate the additional investment costs, the set of refurbishment measures which lead to the further savings also influence the additional turnover to a large extent. As described in (Reiter et al., 2021), it is assumed that additional savings can be achieved more easily by motivating building owners to strive for higher refurbishment standards as long as they are planning refurbishment measures anyway (see Figure 2 for 10% extra savings in 2050 compared to the baseline for all European countries).

Figure 2 Investment cost curve for all countries for 10% extra savings in 2050 compared to the baseline in 2050. The legend refers to refurbishment packages described in (Reiter et al., 2021).

To achieve the stated additional investments, buildings which underwent refurbishment in the baseline (P1, P2 and P3 in Figure 2), are better refurbished to achieve additional savings (P4, and higher in Figure 2). Therefore, only the difference between the original status and the new building status is considered as additional savings. To achieve such additional savings, different measures need to be implemented to tap this additional savings potential.³ These cost curves reflect the specific additional investment costs per kWh saved.

Subsidies which are addressing these additional savings beyond the baseline are one option to tap the efficiency potential and are implemented in some European countries (e.g., (Jakob et al., 2015)) and

³ More details on the implementation and design of the cost curves for additional savings beyond the baseline can be found in (Reiter et al., 2021).

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can help to reduce energy demand and greenhouse gas emissions beyond the regulatory minimum. Alternatively, more stringent building codes and regulations for building refurbishment need to be implemented.

One further aspect can also be mentioned in terms of changes in turnover due to additional refurbishment measures. As the energy efficiency of the building increases due to the insulation of the building envelope, the peak heat demand decreases. Therefore, not only the heat demand decreases but also the installed maximum capacity of the heating system can be decreased. This effect becomes relevant in case, the heating system needs to be replaced, either at the same time, the building is refurbished or at a later stage. Apparent, that the peak capacity reduction is largest, in case the building is refurbished to the highest standard. Depending on the building type, the building size and age class, the cost reduction and therefore, the reduced turnover for heating system manufacturers and installers is of relevant magnitude.

4 Conclusion

As described in the introduction, multiple benefits of energy efficiency measures exist in the building sector which need to be considered when designing new or improving existing support policies to accelerate the uptake of refurbishment measures in the building stock. These non-energy benefits can help to further mobilize the necessary capital for the refurbishment of the existing buildings. In different publications, these effects have been described and partially quantified, either by direct parameter quantification or by evaluating the willingness to pay for efficiency improvement.

Relevant approaches are undertaken to reduce the barriers of quantifying the non-energy benefits to increase awareness and accountability of such measures. Nevertheless, the challenges to provide a comprehensive analysis of all costs and benefits of energy efficiency measures regarding the whole building stock remain high. To quantify the non-energy benefits of the energy efficiency measures modelled in this project, various assumptions and simplifications had to be considered to overcome missing data, filling data gaps or unknown variables and dynamics that could not be captured by the applied model and therefore, the uncertainty in the results remain high. This uncertainty could be reduced by including empirical data which most previous studies used at least partly, to quantify non-energy benefits, however, such empirical data collection was not part of the scope of this deliverable (1.3).

However, based on the data at hand, we were able to quantify the additional turnover based on the different refurbishment measures for all European countries and as the dataset is available, further analyses can be conducted on country level. We also derive first insights into the split-incentive problem, with the respective shares of the investments need to be carried by either the building owner and landlord or the tenants, respectively. Further additions to these findings can be provided within the deliverable 1.4 of this project which is focusing on the policy landscape regarding the energy efficiency first principle. In this context, further insights are expected on e.g., the regulations regarding the split-incentive, the level of subsidies and subsidy schemes and their focus points, including non-energy benefits.

Additionally, to the results shown, we provide with our model results the data basis for other, more system wide energy models to quantify further non-energy benefits as stated in section 2.2. Based on the calculations introduced in the results section 3, on the investments and the respective energy reference area, additional non-energy benefits can be quantified within the energy system model of this project.

However, there are still measures that are not quantifiable in a way that they cannot be addressed with sufficient certainty in the long run as either their impact is low, their metrics are limited, or the rebound effects are reducing the expected savings of such measures. In this context, further work needs to be done to improve panel data or to conduct empirical socio-economic studies with the focus on quantifications of non-energy benefits. The difficulty exists to conclude from specific studies conducted in one country under given circumstances and designed control variables on other countries with differing regulatory or climatic boundary conditions.

In the example of health benefits from increasing the ventilation rate in school buildings, country differences in terms of the age structure of school buildings, equipment rates of ventilation systems,

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climatic boundary conditions and more student related control parameters such as the age of the pupils, etc. need to be addressed to understand the potentials of transferring the results of that study on European level. Additionally, data on ventilation rates of mechanical ventilation systems, as well as the information on the level of total area ventilated needs to be improved and included in the study to allow for better quantification of such non-energy benefits. However, the complexity of the models at hand increases manifold if too many additional parameters need to be considered on European level.

In other cases of non-energy benefits, the model framework needs to be adjusted to allow for better quantification of such parameters. In some parts, e.g., the introduction of GIS-based building stock modelling would better allow for the quantification and assessment of the embodied energy in the building stock compared to the results at hand. The representation on building level better allows for the inclusion of additional parameters to quantify non-energy benefits, especially related to e.g., noise impacts and noise reductions along streets, the alleviation of energy poverty considering the relevant neighbourhood parameters (building types, social structure, etc.) or the reduction of air pollution in combination with the respective heating systems. The combination of such data together with the GIS information on the building level then allows for better quantification of further non-energy benefits.

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